

Effect of D-D Mixture on some Nutrients of a Saline Sodic Soil

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Manuscript received 5 April 1974 ; revised 18 September 1974 ; accepted 18 November 1974

The effects of different doses of D-D mixture, a well known nematocide, on some characteristics of a sodic saline soil were examined. The results revealed significant favourable and toxic responses of the fumigant on N,P,K and organic matter of the soil with passage of time. There was no marked effect on the pH and electrical conductivity. The results have been explained on the basis of microbial activity.

PESTICIDES are widely used in agricultural production. They are used as insecticides, herbicides, fungicides and nematocides. Their use is attendant with varied physical, chemical and biological changes in soils.^{1,2} Some work on the major nutrient availability in soils in presence of pesticides has been reported by Freney³, Castro⁴, Wedding et al.⁵, Alexander⁶, Thiels⁷ as well as Shanker and Kumar.⁸ Their findings are, however, not entirely in agreement. Since the pH changes and nutrient availability have a profound influence on crop production, and since the use of pesticides in agriculture is increasing, it was thought worth-while to examine the effects of different concentrations at various intervals of time of an important nematocide viz., a 50:50 mixture of 1,3 dichloropropene and 1,2 dichloropropane on the nutrient availability (N,P,K and organic matter) in a widely occurring sodic saline soil. Effects on pH and EC are also recorded.

Experimental

The soil used in the study (depth 0-30 cm) was collected from a representative area of Aligarh district. It was dried, crushed and sieved through 4 mm sieve. The general characteristics of the soil were determined and yielded the following data : pH=9.31, E.C.=26.3 $\times 10^{-4}$ mhos/cm, available nitrogen 0.0028%, available phosphorous=0.0006%, available potassium=0.0053% and organic matter = 0.291%

The fumigant used was D-D, a mixture of 1,3

of other hydrocarbons.

The experiments were conducted in earthenware pots of 25 \times 25 cm size. The pots were cleaned and coated with coaltar to prevent adsorption of water. Two kg of the soil was taken in each of the 18 pots.

Zero day samples were then drawn from the pots. The soil was then saturated with 20% distilled water by weight. Six concentrations of D-D mixture (0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 ml) were injected at a depth of 15 cm in three replications without growing any crop. All the samples were then watered with 100 ml distilled water per week throughout the period of experiments. Distilled water was used to avoid any contamination with impurities. Samples were drawn at an interval of 15 days upto 90 days and the effects of the nematocide on pH, EC, N,P,K and organic matter measured.

The pH of the samples was measured in 1:2 soil water suspension with a pH meter with glass and calomel saturated electrode assembly. Electrical conductivity was measured with Philips conductivity meter with dip type cell at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ on the 1:2 soil water suspension. Organic matter was estimated as per Walkley and Black's method.⁹ Available nitrogen was estimated as per alkaline KMnO_4 method.¹⁰ Available phosphorous was determined colorimetrically by Olsen's method.¹¹ Available potassium was estimated turbiditometrically^{1,2} with turbidity measured by Bausch and Lomb spectronic '20' at 660 nm with a red filter.

Results and Discussion

The influence of D D mixture on organic matter, available N,P,K of a sodic saline soil is expressed in Table 1. Each reading in the table for individual doses represents a mean of seven values recorded at 0,15,30, 45, 60, 75 and 90 days after application of the fumigant. Similarly the average values for different days represent a mean of several values obtained at different doses viz., 0.0, 0.50, 1.00, 1.50, 2.00 and 2.50 ml per 2 kg soil. The results were subjected to statistical analysis and variance ratio, and LSD values were calculated using the value of t at 5% level of significance. In the discussion that follows, the average values for doses and days have been considered and the term significant is used as meaning statistically significant at 5% F level (2.52 for doses and 2.42 for days).

Effect on pH and EC: No significant changes in pH or electrical conductivity either with increase in doses of D-D mixture or with interval of time was observed in the fumigated samples.

Effect on organic matter : The data given in Table 1 showed a significant decline in organic matter content of the soil with increasing applications of D-D mixture. With passage of time, however, there was a significant rise upto 30 days and thereafter a continuous decline. The decline in organic matter can be explained by the fact that while fumigates like D-D greatly eliminate nematode population, many soil bacteria are fairly resistant to fumigants. The eradicator type chemicals produce greater re-invasion potentials¹³ with the result that the reactivated soil organisms bring about a rapid decomposition of organic matter which significantly declines. Such effects have also been reported by Smith and Wenzel¹⁴ as well as others in case of soils treated with chlorinated insecticides.

TABLE I—EFFECT OF D-D MIXTURE ON NUTRIENT AVAILABILITY FOR DIFFERENT DOSES OF THE MIXTURE AT VARIOUS INTERVALS OF TIME.

Applications : Doses (in ml per two kg of soil)/days	Average values of available nutrients for various doses and days in mg per 100 gm soil			
	Organic matter	Nitrogen	Phosphorous	Potassium
0.0	337.120	7.190	0.720	11.170
0.5	336.270	7.450	0.970	10.550
1.0	331.080	7.750	0.940	10.150
1.5	328.050	7.830	0.940	9.990
2.0	322.130	7.380	0.850	10.920
2.5	315.850	7.060	0.780	10.980
LSD	9.100	0.371	0.094	0.580
Variance ratio	9.407	7.819	9.660	7.849
0 days	294.120	2.800	0.600	5.250
15 days	335.060	8.710	0.950	10.720
30 days	358.530	9.420	1.120	13.410
45 days	354.970	8.550	1.030	13.170
60 days	328.080	7.880	0.790	10.810
75 days	316.650	7.550	0.740	11.010
90 days	311.699	7.180	0.680	10.020
LSD	8.320	0.340	0.086	0.530
Variance ratio	65.050	334.590	42.750	215.420

Effect on available nitrogen : Examination of the data given in Table I generally indicated increase in available nitrogen with increasing doses of D-D mixture upto a value of 1.5 ml per 2 kg of soil after which it declined. A significant rise also occurred with passage of time, reached a maximum at 30 days and thereafter declined. The initial increase in available nitrogen was due to the decomposition of soil organic matter by fumigant resistant bacteria¹³ which resulted in the release of nitrogen. The decrease with large doses on the other hand appeared to be due to the inhibitory effects of large doses of fumigant of nitrification. The findings were in the agreement with the work of Walcott and co-workers¹⁵ and Koike.¹⁶ The decline with passage of time was due to the dissipation of the toxic chemical and reinfestation of high potential zones of the treated soil by the fast growing fungi of vigorously competitive sugar and amino acid utilising kinds. The results were in agreement with the findings of Kreutzer.¹⁷

Effect on available phosphorus : A reference to the results given in Table I generally indicated a significant increase in phosphorous availability upto 1.5 ml of D-D mixture per two kg of soil and upto 30 days of

its application followed by a significant decline in both cases. Wensley¹⁸ and Martin and co-workers¹⁹ have reported increased and highly stimulated microbial activity in soil as a result of fumigation. The effects of reinfested fungus flora, ascomycetes and actinomycetes resulted in the decomposition of soil organic matter bringing about a gradual increase in phosphorous availability till a maxima was reached both with doses and passage of time. However, the toxic effect of too high doses, and certain chemical reactions like reduction of phosphorous to PH_3 with passage of time resulted in the decline of phosphorous.

Effect on available potassium : A reference to Table I revealed that potassium availability generally decreased with increasing application of D-D mixture upto 1.5 ml per 2 kg of soil and thereafter increased. With passage of time it increased upto 30 days and thereafter followed a fluctuating pattern. The mechanism by which the fluctuation occurred was not entirely clear. The suppressive influence on potassium availability in soil was probably the tendency of the fumigant to fix available potassium into non exchangeable form on the clay lattice but further work is required to justify this conclusion.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. Abrar Mustafa Khan, Professor of Botany, Aligarh Muslim University, for helpful suggestions.

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